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“INSTRUCTIONAL LEADERSHIP IN PHILIPPINE K–12 SCHOOLS: A HYBRID FRAMEWORK FOR EDUCATIONAL IMPROVEMENT”

The implementation of the K–12 curriculum reform in 2012 with landscape of education in the Philippines that evolved dramatically over the past decade. This reform is one of the most significant educational initiatives in recent Philippine history, aimed to align the country's basic education system with international standards and prepare learners for higher education, job opportunities and some business venture. In this context, instructional leadership has emerged as a vital force for driving educational quality and student achievement. However, the success of any curriculum reform depends not only on its content but also on how it is implemented and led within schools with government and stakeholders' support.

School leaders are expected to be instructional leaders but are rarely empowered or supported to fulfill this critical role effectively. This means that instructional leadership is one of the functions of school leaders which has an effect of teaching and learning. The challenge of this responsibility is due to lack of support in designing program and project on instructional leadership, limited access to instructional materials, and too heavy administrative duties.

These challenges could be addressed as a result of research that provide a conceptual framework that integrates some leadership theories: Hallinger's instructional leadership, Leithwood's transformational leadership, and Spillane's distributed leadership. The combinations of these models, a hybrid approach to instructional leadership can be developed such the case of the K-12 program with realities and constraints that is experienced by the teachers on the implementation of this curriculum.

Effective instructional leadership show focus on defining the school's mission, managing the instructional program, and promoting a positive school climate. This model emphasizes clear goals, instructional supervision, and a structured learning environment. However, instructional leaders are not expert in designing instructional materials, thus, it could be one of the reasons, why curriculum does not meet some of it expected outputs.

While models of instructional leadership influence curriculum design and provide a foundation of the instructional system, however, in the implementation, is a different area to consider. Because, instructional design as describe as hybrid a combination of traditional and blended it with technology-based, in which this instructional design maybe egocentric, principal-centric and which is not addressing the relationship between conceptual and emotional aspects of leadership.

Instructional leadership is a shared practice distributed across teachers, department heads, and other stakeholders who contribute to decision-making and instructional improvement. This approach recognizes the complexity of schools and the value of collaboration in addressing multifaceted challenges. This is a consultative approach to teachers, parents, students and the community. The problem is from the grassroots so that distribution of shared responsibilities lies on the heart of the people and its instructional leader as a transformative leader as well. In the actual setting, because of the constraint of resources, principal and teacher sometimes shoulder the expenses especially on identifying and tapping into the expertise of individual and on initiative to support the instructional system designing. Workshop and training entail big budget; thus, it is the ability of the instructional leaders to address this component to achieve its desired goals and objectives.

Embedding these values in leadership practices, schools can create more cohesive and empowered learning communities. Shared leadership acknowledges a feeling of ownership and transparency where school's instructional direction is more likely to meet its success that is when teachers and staff are involved in shaping participatory approach in relation to Filipino cultural values like "bayanihan," or community cooperation.

Another hybrid framework is the commitment to ongoing professional development. There are educators attend seminars that are not their subject being taught which they attend for compliance purposes, hence the training is not in the context of their expertise. This happened in a small school where teachers have taught subjects not a on their educational background. Unfortunately, this is happening on the ground and sad to note, that identification of whom to be trained is based on personal choice of some principal rather on teachers' fitness and desired criteria to attend a particular training. Hence, teachers and school leaders

need to update teaching strategies to enhance their instructional leadership and skills and to abreast with curriculum changes, and reflect on their practice.

As schools become centers for cooperative inquiry and professional development, instructional quality will likely improve in a sustained and meaningful way in a more result-oriented approach would be to establish school-based or cluster-based professional enhancement. Instructional leaders, including principals and master teachers, should be equipped not only in content and pedagogy but also in facilitating learning. These could include peer observations approach, lesson study counselling groups, coaching cycles, and action research approach.

Effective instructional leaders must be able to adapt strategies to their specific context, taking into account factors such as socioeconomic conditions, community involvement, linguistic diversity, and available resources where contextual responsiveness and recognizes that leadership cannot be “one-size-fits-all.” The needs, challenges, and strengths of schools vary from one school to others. A public high school faces very different realities from a rural elementary school, hence instructional materials is based on contextualization, localization and indigenization.

By grounded leadership practices in local realities, schools can implement more significant and sustainable improvements on its instructional system. In geographically isolated and disadvantaged areas (GIDAs), leaders may need to realize more on resource mobilization and community engagement to support instructional objectives. In multilingual regions, instructional leaders must support culture- based pedagogy and instruction which is accessible to all learners.

The adoption of this hybrid instructional leadership framework carries several implications for practice, policy, and capacity building.

First, policy support is important. National and regional education leaders should allocate funding for sustained, context-specific professional development programs rather than one-off workshops. Leadership functions provide clear guidelines for group effort collaborative decision-making within schools. The Department of Education (DepEd) must identify the value of shared and distributed leadership in its governance frameworks. Policies should encourage decentralization of certain instructional system.

Second, capacity building must be given priority. Many principals and instructional leaders have limited training in instructional supervision, coaching, or curriculum leadership because they are not instructional system design expert. These programs should be included on relearning components on training and workshop, such as mentoring, case study analysis, and leadership practicum, to connect the gap between theory and its practice. The integration of the principles of instructional, transformational, and distributed leadership is crucial to design leadership development programs.

Third, community engagement should be strengthened. School leaders should actively support partnerships with groups in the community and it should involve in school improvement planning, and create feedback system to ensure that the instructional leadership and instructional system are fully implemented. Parents, local government units (LGUs), non-governmental organizations, and other community stakeholders all have a role to play in supporting teaching and learning because schools cannot improve instruction in isolation.

Finally, data can give continuous improvement and help re-designed successful practices to all schools with monitoring and evaluation mechanisms that needs to be improved. These may include teacher satisfaction

surveys, instructional audits, learning outcomes analysis, and case documentation. Hence, instructional leadership initiatives must be accompanied by tools and indicators to assess their impact.

Instructional leadership must move beyond a limited focus on administrative oversight and become a changing force for teaching and learning. By integrating the structured focus of Hallinger's instructional leadership, the motivational drive of Leithwood's transformational leadership, and the collaborative standards of Spillane's distributed leadership, the proposed hybrid framework offers a systemic and context-sensitive approach to educational leadership and instruction system. The evolving demands of Philippine basic education, driven by curriculum reforms, global trends, and local challenges, require an in-depth analysis of school leadership.

This paper challenges to view leadership not as the responsibility of a single individual, but as a shared endeavor rooted in trust, collaboration, and a deep commitment to students' learning. This is not a prescriptive solution but a suggestion as instructional guide that supports school leaders, educators, policymakers, and stakeholders to analyze on their current practices and explore new possibilities on instructional leadership.

In creating the conditions in which every teacher can teach well, every student can learn deeply, and every school can thrive within its unique context embracing this model, Philippine educational system can move closer to realizing the objectives of the K-12 reform but in strengthening the quality of education to every learner. Ultimately, effective and efficient instructional leadership is not about controlling classroom management but an independent instructional leadership with a common goal to provide basic education as right to every Filipino child.